

WELL-BEING OF NON-READERS IN TANTANGAN 1 DISTRICT: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The definition of reading has moved beyond decoding printed symbols and recognizing words, thus, reading is a process of constructing meaning to a written text. It is a dream of any teacher that every student may acquire knowledge, skill, and understanding to combat the challenges of life in order to meet the global demands. The study aimed to explore the well-being of non-readers in the Tantangan 1 district. This research used qualitative research which is a research approach that allows the researcher to interpret the life of people to understand their problems better and deeper to generate solutions that are relevant to their situations. The participants of the study are 10 teachers with tagged non-readers in their class for the school year 2023-2024. A semi-structured guide survey questionnaire was used to collect the necessary information and responses from the participants of the study. Thematic analysis was used to process the responses of the participants. On how non-reader pupils in your class access and engage with information and knowledge in your daily activities theme that was generated based on the teacher-participants was Varied Teaching and Learning Strategies. On how they overcome the challenges as a non-reader in their class in daily activities in school, the generated theme was Various Strategies and Support Systems based on the responses of the teacher-participants. Finally, On the best practices of class/school to ensure the well-being of the tagged non-readers of their class/school and are those best practices effective in promoting the well-being of your pupils the formulated theme was individualized instruction

Keywords: *Well-being, Non-readers, Case study, Tantangan*

INTRODUCTION

Every Filipino child needs to be provided with quality, equitable, and complete basic education. The Department of Education in the Philippines implements various mechanisms to ensure that no one among the children is left behind, guarantee inclusive and equitable quality education, and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. It has been a perennial problem of the teachers and the school about the reading ability of pupils though there are many interventions made by the teachers.

To strengthen this program, the Department of Education issued the DepEd Order No. 45, series of 2002 to enforce the policy that “school children must be a reader by Grade 3 and that no child be promoted to Grade 4 unless he shows mastery of the basic literacy skills”.

In response to the increasing number of struggling readers and poor reading comprehension of learners in public schools, which is a common problem in the Philippine education system, the Department of Education (DepEd) used several intervention programs to equip elementary pupils with higher levels of learning and to give support for those children who are left behind in reading and writing. The Department of Education implements various programs to respond to the struggling readers’ needs. Some of the programs implemented were the Pull-Out Scheme, Remedial Reading Class, Summer Reading Camp, and Feeding Program.

In detail, the Pull-Out Scheme is a program that directs the identified non-readers to report to the reading session during the agreed schedule for intensive instruction or session under the trained reading teacher. On the other hand, the “Remedial Reading Class” is an intervention that helps reduce the number of pupils who have extreme difficulty in reading and writing. During summer, there is a “Summer Reading Camp” for the identified frustrated readers. These readers are taught how to read for two weeks during summer. Meanwhile, there is this “School Feeding Program”, which works on the nutrition of the children to enhance their school performance.

Despite the efforts and initiatives of the Department of Education, there are gaps and problems encountered in the implementation of the reading program. In fact, the teachers and administrators face different obstacles in various reading interventions. The challenges they encounter include the classroom size, learner’s attitudes and behaviors, resources and parent involvement.

Consequently, the result of the 2018 Programmed International Student Assessment (PISA) revealed that Filipino students ranked last among the 79 countries and got a rating of 340 which is the lowest score in reading comprehension. The result reflects the poor performance in reading comprehension of Filipino students and recognizes the gaps in attaining the quality of basic education in our country.

Similarly, the performance of the Grade 6 students in the National Achievement Test (NAT) has been declining in the last three years based on the Regional Memorandum 157, series of 2019. The national average mean percentage score (MPS) in grade 6 continued its downward trajectory at 37.44 which is the weakest performance in the history of DepEd. In addition, the Phil-IRI results also showed an increasing number of frustrated readers with poor reading comprehension based on the results of 2012-2015 data.

With these challenges, the researcher is propagated to conduct an evaluation research to the well-being of Non-readers of Tantaran 1 District.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of this study is to explore the live experiences of Non-readers of Tantaran 1 District, and go deeper into the heart of the issue and to bring the point of view, perceptions, insights, and feelings of the participants. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the challenges encountered by the pupils in their reading class?
2. What are the coping mechanisms of the pupils in overcoming their difficulties in reading class?
3. What are possible school programs may craft to ensure the well-being of nonreaders?

METHODOLOGY

The study uses qualitative research in particularly case study. Which is a research approach that allows the researcher to interpret the life of people to understand their problems better and deeper to generate solutions that are relevant to their situations, Wa-Ambaleka (2018).

The respondents of the study will be ten (10) elementary teachers in Tantaran 1 for the school year 2023-2024 with following inclusion criteria, a. teachers must be permanent or regular, b. must be at least 3 to five years in the teaching in public schools, c with nonreader pupils. Thematic analysis was use to process the responses of the participants of the study.

RESULTS

On the challenges encountered by the pupils in their reading class. The theme that was generated based on the teacher-participants was **Varied Teaching and Learning Strategies**.

On how they overcome the challenges as a non-reader in their class in daily activities in school in connection with the challenges, the generated theme was **Various Strategies and Support Systems**.

On the best practices of class/school to ensure the well-being of the tagged non-readers of their class/school and are those best practices effective in promoting the well-being of your

pupils. Based on the responses of the participants the formulated theme was **individualized instruction**

DISCUSSION

On the challenges encountered by the pupils in their reading class

The theme that was generated based on the teacher-participants was **Varied Teaching and Learning Strategies**.

Reading is a vital basic skill that a learner needs to develop to succeed in school. Reading is a cognitive process that involves decoding symbols to arrive at meaning. It is an active process of constructing meanings of words. Reading with a purpose helps the reader to direct information towards a goal and focuses their attention.

With this, teachers are doing their best to have a meaningful teaching and learning process. The teacher participants shared their experiences as;

*“In my classroom, catering to non-reader pupils involves employing a variety of multisensory approaches to ensure they can access and engage with information effectively. Firstly, visual aids play a crucial role, such as using pictures, charts, and diagrams to convey concepts and instructions. Secondly, incorporating hands-on activities allows these students to interact with materials tangibly, facilitating better understanding. Thirdly, utilizing auditory resources such as recorded instructions or storytelling helps convey information in a different modality. Additionally, kinesthetic learning experiences, such as movement-based activities or manipulative tools, enable students to physically explore concepts. Lastly, peer support and collaboration create opportunities for these pupils to learn from their peers and participate actively in group tasks, fostering a sense of inclusivity and shared learning experiences. By integrating these strategies, non-reader students can effectively access and engage with the content presented in our daily activities”. **Participant 1, Teacher I, and Female***

“To support non-reader pupils, I implement a multi-sensory strategy. Firstly, I utilize visual aids like diagrams, pictures, and videos to convey concepts and reinforce understanding beyond text. Secondly, hands-on experiments and manipulatives provide experiential learning opportunities, aiding in grasping abstract ideas directly. Additionally, auditory resources such as recorded lectures or podcasts cater to auditory learners. I also promote peer collaboration and discussion, fostering verbal communication and group learning. Finally, I leverage educational technology, including apps and software, to deliver interactive lessons tailored to diverse learning styles. These approaches ensure active participation and success for non-reader pupils, contributing to a supportive and inclusive learning

environment”. **Participant 2, Teacher I, and Female;**

*For non-reader pupils in the class, it is essential to provide alternative ways for them to access and engage with information and knowledge through different strategies like providing visual aids, giving them hands-on activities, peer support, technology integration, and most of all encouragement and support. By implementing these strategies and creating a supportive learning environment, non-reader pupils can effectively access and engage with information and knowledge alongside their peers in daily classroom activities. **Participant 3, and Teacher II***

The result of the study is related to the statement of Anonat (2011) states that Reading is an important skill to develop because it is fundamental to a person to function in today’s society like assuming duties and responsibilities in a day-to-day activity. Also, reading develops critical thinking as it allows the learner to imagine, infer, predict, conclude, and draw judgments among other skills. In addition, it allows the learner to discover new things. Through reading books, magazines, and articles on the internet, the learners will become aware of the latest innovations and discoveries in various fields.

On how they overcome the challenges as a non-reader in their class in daily activities in school

In connection with the challenges, the generated theme was **Various Strategies and Support Systems** based on the responses of the teacher-participants as they share:

*“In my class, non-readers face a unique set of challenges in their daily activities at school. However, they often overcome these obstacles through various strategies and support systems. Firstly, they rely heavily on visual aids and hands-on learning experiences provided by teachers. These might include diagrams, charts, and models that help them grasp concepts without relying solely on written text. Additionally, peer support plays a crucial role as classmates often assist non-readers by explaining instructions or clarifying content. Teachers also adapt teaching methods, incorporating multimedia resources and interactive activities to accommodate diverse learning styles. Furthermore, non-readers may develop compensatory skills such as strong listening and observation abilities to compensate for their reading difficulties. Finally, schools often offer specialized interventions and support services tailored to the needs of non-readers, providing additional resources and assistance as necessary to ensure their academic success. Through these approaches, non-readers can effectively navigate the challenges they encounter in the classroom and actively engage in their educational journey”. **Participant 1, Teacher I, and Female;***

“Non-readers face significant challenges in navigating daily activities in school, but there are various strategies they can employ to overcome these obstacles. Firstly, they often rely heavily on auditory cues and verbal

instructions provided by teachers and peers. Active listening becomes paramount, as they must absorb information through lectures, discussions, and oral explanations. Additionally, non-readers may utilize alternative methods of accessing written content, such as audio recordings or assistive technology like screen readers. Collaborating with classmates who can assist in interpreting written materials or providing summaries can also be beneficial. Moreover, cultivating strong communication skills enables non-readers to advocate for themselves and express their needs to teachers and support staff effectively. By embracing these strategies and seeking support when necessary, non-readers can successfully navigate the challenges of school and participate fully in academic and social activities”.
Participant 2 Teacher I, and Female;

“Non-readers face significant challenges in a classroom setting where literacy skills are essential. To overcome these obstacles, they often rely heavily on auditory instruction and verbal communication. In daily activities, non-readers may actively engage with teachers and peers to gather information through listening and asking questions. They might also use alternative learning strategies, such as visual aids, hands-on activities, or digital resources that don't heavily rely on text. Additionally, collaboration with classmates who can read may be key, as they can provide support and assistance in understanding written instructions or materials. With determination and support from teachers and peers, non-readers can navigate their daily school activities successfully”.
Participant 4 Teacher III, and Female;

“As a teacher, I utilize personalized learning plans, explicit instruction, and visual aids to support nonreaders in improving their reading skills. Interactive read-aloud sessions and small group instruction foster active participation and create a supportive learning environment. Collaboration with families and consistent encouragement helps boost confidence and motivation. Ongoing assessment allows for adjustments to instruction based on nonreaders' needs. Overall, these strategies aim to create an inclusive environment where nonreaders feel empowered to succeed in reading both at school and at home”.
Participant 10, Teacher III, and Female

With the result of the study, as Fosudo (2010) affirms that the acquisition of reading skills has a beneficial effect on all school subjects, including social studies, science, mathematics, and so on. Poor reading skills can make a child develop a poor attitude toward school and can create self-esteem problems later in life.

The reading skill of the pupils is very important to have a meaningful teaching and learning process. Thus, nonreaders overcome the challenges in their class with the help of their teachers.

On the best practices of class/school to ensure the well-being of the tagged non-readers of their class/school and are those best practices effective in promoting the well-being of your pupils

Based on the responses of the participants the formulated theme was **individualized instruction**.

Individualized instruction is an effective teaching strategy for at-risk students. From Socrates' recitation to L. Vygotsky's scaffolding, educators have used many flavors of individualized instruction to reach each child. Individualized instruction can be broken down into two major components: learning and motivation. To individualize instruction for at-risk students, the teacher needs to choose flexible strategies that allow for student differences. Effective individualized learning hooks new material to prior knowledge, recognizing the child's culture and experiences.

The teacher participants shared their best practices such as:

“In our school, we employ a variety of best practices to ensure the well-being of non-readers in our classes. One approach we find effective is individualized instruction, where we tailor learning materials and activities to meet the unique needs of each non-reader. We also implement small group instruction to provide targeted support, allowing us to focus on specific skills and concepts. Peer support and collaboration play a crucial role as well, as we pair non-readers with peers who can serve as mentors or reading buddies, fostering a sense of belonging and community. Additionally, we create a supportive classroom environment where students feel safe to take risks and ask for help, while also celebrating their progress and achievements through positive reinforcement. While these practices require flexibility and ongoing evaluation, we find that they are effective in promoting the well-being of our pupils by providing them with the necessary support, resources, and encouragement to thrive academically and emotionally”. **Participant 1, Teacher II, and Female;**

“In our classroom, we prioritize the well-being of non-readers through a combination of individualized instruction, small group support, and a nurturing classroom environment. We recognize that each student has unique needs and learning styles, so we tailor instruction to meet those needs, whether it's through hands-on activities, visual aids, or peer collaboration. By providing a supportive and inclusive atmosphere, we create a safe space where non-readers feel comfortable taking risks and asking for help. Our continuous assessment and monitoring ensure that we can adjust our approaches as needed to support their growth. Through these practices, we've seen positive outcomes in terms of both academic progress and emotional well-being. Students feel valued, motivated, and empowered to overcome challenges, fostering a sense of confidence and belonging in our classroom community”. **Participant 2, Teacher I, and Female;**

“In our class/school, we prioritize the well-being of non-readers by implementing several best practices. Firstly, we create a supportive and inclusive environment where students feel safe to express their challenges and receive personalized support. Individualized learning plans are developed to cater to their specific needs, incorporating strategies such as one-on-one tutoring, small group instruction, and multisensory approaches to literacy. Additionally, we offer regular opportunities for non-readers to engage in alternative forms of expression and communication, such as art, music, and oral storytelling, to build confidence and self-esteem. These practices are highly effective in promoting the well-being of our pupils, as they not only address academic difficulties but also foster a sense of belonging and accomplishment, ultimately empowering non-readers to reach their full potential”. **Participant 4, Teacher I, and Female;**

“In my class, ensuring the well-being of non-readers involves several best practices. I created a supportive and inclusive environment where students feel comfortable expressing their challenges with reading. I offer personalized support through one-on-one tutoring or small-group instruction”. **Participant 5, Teacher II, and Female;**

“Best practices include using visual aids, hands-on activities, peer support through reading buddies, and personalized education plans. These practices effectively promote the well-being of non-readers by catering to their individual needs and creating a supportive learning environment”. **Participant 6, Teacher II, and Female;**

“Best practices for ensuring the well-being of non-readers in our class/school include providing alternative forms of communication, such as visuals and hands-on activities, assigning reading buddies for peer support, and offering personalized assistance through individualized education plans (IEPs). These practices are effective in promoting the well-being of our pupils by addressing their unique needs and fostering a supportive learning environment”. **Participant 7, Teacher III, and Female;**

“To accommodate the diverse learning needs and boost the confidence in learning, the following are the best practices that show effectiveness in promoting the well-being of our pupils (non-readers), a. Creating a supportive classroom environment, b. Encouraging cooperative learning and peer support, c. We offer differentiated activities or instruction, d. Provide them with hands-on activities and visual aids”. **Participant 9, Teacher II, and Female;**

“In our classroom, we prioritize the well-being of non-readers through a combination of individualized instruction, small group support, and a nurturing classroom environment. We recognize that each student has unique needs and learning styles, so we tailor instruction to meet those needs, whether it's through hands-on activities, visual aids, or peer

collaboration. By providing a supportive and inclusive atmosphere, we create a safe space where non-readers feel comfortable taking risks and asking for help. Our continuous assessment and monitoring ensure that we can adjust our approaches as needed to support their growth. Through these practices, we've seen positive outcomes in terms of both academic progress and emotional well-being. Students feel valued, motivated, and empowered to overcome challenges, fostering a sense of confidence and belonging in our classroom community". **Participant 10, Teacher II, and Female**

The result of the study is associated with the effective teaching practices in handling non-readers comprising the use of teachers' adjustments, strategies and scaffolds to establish reading mastery, exposing them to letter sounds, and short stories, and the use of follow-up. WH questions enhanced their reading performance significantly. Variations of reading teachers' nature as an enabler, a facilitator, a humanist, a behaviorist, and an expert, as regards to their teaching practices, were proven significant to students' reading effectiveness (Davis, 2016).

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

Varied teaching and learning strategies are used by the teachers who handle tagged non-readers in the Tantaran 1 district.

Support System and Various Strategies used by the Teachers to overcome challenges in handling tagged non-readers.

Finally, individualized instructions is the best practices of class/school to ensure the well-being of the tagged non-readers of their class/school and are those best practices effective in promoting the well-being of your pupils.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented;

The school may close supervision will have to be conducted by school administrators to observe reading teachers and find ways to conduct training on the enhancement of teaching adjustments, strategies, and scaffolds that will improve teaching practices in the teaching of reading. The teachers may continue their best practices to eradicate non-readers in the school. That this study be replicated in wide scope to have a clearer picture quantitatively and may add variables not included in the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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